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Research Article

**RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF HYSTEOSALPINGOGRAPHY
(HSG) AND HYSTEOSCOPY: COMBINED PROCEDURE AS A
FIRST LINE INFERTILITY WORK UP**¹Habib Ali, ²Madiha Nawaz, ³Iqra Tariq¹Aziz Bhatti Shaheed Teaching Hospital Gujrat, Habibali11@gmail.com²Pakistan Ordinance Factories Hospital, Wah Cantt, Madihanawaz05024@gmail.com³Salamar Institute of Health Sciences, Lahore, Iqrakms2013@gmail.com**Abstract:**

Background- For analyzing the life structures and form of uterine pit alongside fallopian cylinders and its patency HSG is generally used in the first line. In case of infertility in couples, peritoneal hole by indicative hysteroscopy and video endoscopic assessment of endometrial may be used due to the some limitations in the HSG.

Objective- To examine the handiness of hysteroscopy and HSG as a consolidated method in a solitary setting to distinguish uterine pathologies as a barrenness work up.

Design of study- Retrospective analysis was done in this study

Methodology- In this study total 365 women were selected who were infertile and on them HSG and hysteroscopy was done

Findings- In this study abnormality of intrauterine was observed in 161 patients, and out of these 161 patients 35 were suffered from hyperplastic endometrium, 22 in adhesions of intrauterine, 52 in uterine septum and in 28 blockage of tubes was also observed

Conclusion- In this study by the HSG and hysteroscopy, thorough diagnosis of uterus and tubes was done. There are many positive aspects of this study for example it is cost viable, assures the comfort of patients, and yield in good understanding of all the minor and major identifications.

Keywords: Infertility ;Hysterosalpingography; Hysteroscopy;

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INTRODUCTION:

In 10 to 15% women the main cause of infertility is the uterine cavity while it was also found that in 50% of women those were suffering infertility also had the problem of abnormality of uterine. To diagnose the problems in the uterine and also to find the blockages in the tubes HSG is used. There are some drawbacks of HSG for example to insert cannula is difficult, study may not be completed due to the leakage in the vagina or cervical stenosis, and also the discomfort of patients. To diagnose any problem in the lower cavity, tubes and endo cervical canals Hysteroscopy is used, it is also performed for the treatment purposes. Following are some indications of the Hysteroscopy: irregular premenopausal, adhesions of intrauterine, fibroids, septum in uterine, and sub mucosal. The situation when the Hysteroscopy is not used, in the time period of pregnancy, in the process of sterilization, when cancer of uterine has been diagnosed, and infection in pelvic. The patients may recover speedily when in the evaluation of hysteroscopy no anesthesia is used. The patients who cannot bear the extensive procedure of hysteroscopy on them anesthesia is used, and anesthesia is also used on the patients who cannot bear the intense monitoring process of hysteroscopy on them it is must to use anesthesia.

There is a lot of research work available on both hysteroscopy and HSG or on both of them, many researcher have done the comparison between the hysteroscopy and HSG. While comparing the HSG and hysteroscopy, hysteroscopy is better than the HSG because in the evaluation of uterine and to diagnose the uterine cavity hysteroscopy gives the more accurate results. HSG gives false results in the diagnostic procedure.

In this study the advantages of both hysteroscopy and HSG is presented, these both procedures are used in this study to diagnose the infertility of the uterine.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was done in Jinnah hospital Lahore by collecting the data from different cases. In this study total cases on which this study was conducted were 356 that means that both hysteroscopy and HSG was

done on all the women to check the reasons of infertility. While selected patients, patient who had primary and secondary infertility were both selected. While selected patients it was checked that either patients had any kind of allergic reaction, fibroids in uterus, genital herpes, any kind of abnormality in the lower tubes or suspected endometriosis. Patients who was facing the problem of infertility from more than 10 years were also excluded.

After observing there all above signs, 356 women were selected then on all of these cases in very first visit, detailed tests was done including blood test, urine tests and transvaginal sonogram. Women whom test results were normal, their husbands were thoroughly monitored. All the patients who were not even able to conceive after passing all these procedure they were selected for the HSG and hysteroscopy.

A written consent agreement were signed from all the women. After that the procedure of hysteroscopy was started by using the normal anesthesia and traditional hysteroscope whose diameter was 4mm and this was kept at the angle of 30 degree. By using this uterine was examined thoroughly that either the women under observation had the problem of uterine cavity or not. At the same time after the evaluation of hysteroscopy HSG was also done by injecting the 20ml water soluble with iodine based dye on the patients under consideration. The entire procedure was thoroughly examined and all the results were noted in a careful way.

RESULT:

In this study abnormality of intrauterine was observed in 161 patients, and out of these 161 patients 35 were the patients of hyperplastic endometrium, in 22 intrauterine adhesions was observed, 52 in uterine septum and in 28 blockage of tubes was diagnosed.

In this study the patients who were selected most of them had the mean age between 26 to 30 years and also in the selected patients majority of the patients were having the problem of infertility from less than five years where as only 28% had the infertility duration of 6 to 10 years.

Table 1. Selection criteria of the patients

Mean age (years)	n=356	(%)
< 20	8	2.2
21-25	35	9.8
26-30	128	35.9
31-35	91	25.5
36-40	74	20.7
>40	20	5.6
Primary infertility	257	72.2
Secondary infertility	99	27.8
1-5	255	71.6
6-10	101	28.4

In selected patients 72% had the primary infertility and 27% had he secondary infertility. In 356 patients total 76 patients that means 21% of patients had tight cervical canal problem. In the same way 9.8% had the problem of endometrium of hyperplastic while 14% had polypoidal endometrium, in 7.8% of the patients observed the blockage of tubes, in 6% genital herpes was observed.

Table 2. Results noted during HSG and Hysteroscopy

Results	n=356	Percentage
Tight cervical canal	76	21
Hyperplastic endometrium	35	9.8
Polypoidal endometrium	52	14.6
Uterine septum	40	11.2
Intra uterine adhesions	22	6
Myoma	12	3.3
Tubal block	28	7.8

Following is the figure 1 in which findings that are described in table 2 is presented the form of bar chart of .

Figure 1. Abnormal intrauterine findings

In the following table 3. There is the intervention that are performed, 71 patients out of 76 were facing the problem of tight cervical canal.

Table 3. Interventions performed in the study population

	Number	Procedure
Tight cervical canal	71	Dilatation
	5	Radial incision/ versa point
Hyperplastic endometrium	35	Curettage
Polypoidal endometrium	41	Curettage
	11	Curettage
Septum	40	Polypectomy
Adhesion	22	Resection

DISCUSSION:

This one of a kind conventional system has the upside of assessing both cylinders and uterus in a similar setting by exact strategy. As the technique was done under general anesthesia tolerant participation, torment, specialized difficulties were sifted through. Arranging definitive employable method in a similar setting should be possible by experienced individual. Term for researching, diagnosing and treating the strange condition can be diminished to the extraordinary degree. Despite the fact that analytic lap hysteroscopy is best quality level, in accurately chose populace pointless laparoscopy can be kept away from by consolidated hysteroscopy and HSG in a similar setting. Uterine cavity irregularities are generally experienced in the barren populace; in this way a precise, cost effective, sheltered and simple technique is required in the first-line assessment of a fruitless couple. HSG meets a lion's share of these essentials. It gives backhanded assessment of the uterine cavity as well as the fallopian tubes. Nonetheless, while an excessive amount of difference material may darken mass injuries, air pockets or clusters may mirror them. Quiet inconvenience, utilization of complexity medium and ionizing radiation are different disadvantages of the procedure. Hysteroscopy effectively acted in an office setting in no time flat, gives direct perception of the cervical waterway and uterine depression, however not the cylinders and a chance to intercede in the analyzed pathology without exceptional patient distress. In addition, endometrial issue that are inflammatory or irresistible in etiology or its hormonal and tropic status can be pictured in hysteroscopy. Past examinations researching the analytic estimation of HSG yielded conflicting results; accordingly supplanting of HSG in a first line fruitlessness workup is under discussion.

In 10 to 15% women the main cause of infertility is the uterine cavity while it was also found that in 50% of women those were suffering infertility also had the problem of abnormality of uterine. To diagnose the blockages in the tubes and the problems in the uterine, HSG is used. There are some limitations of HSG e.g. to insert cannula is difficult, study may not be completed due to the leakage in the vagina or incomplete study due to cervical stenosis, and also the patient discomfort. To diagnose any problem in uterine cavity, endometrium tubes and endo cervical canals Hysteroscopy is performed for the treatment purposes. The patients may recover speedily when in the evaluation of hysteroscopy no anesthesia is used. The patients who cannot bear the intensive procedure of hysteroscopy on them anesthesia is used, and anesthesia is also used on the patients who cannot bear the intensive monitoring in the hysteroscopy procedure

In this study the patients who were selected most of them had the mean age between 26 to 30 years and also in the selected patients majority of the patients were having the problem of infertility from less than five years where as only 28% had the infertility duration of 6 to 10 years.

In this study abnormality of intrauterine was observed in 161 patients, and out of these 161 patients, 22 intrauterine adhesions was observed, 35 were the patients of hyperplastic endometrium, 52 in genital herpes was observed.

CONCLUSION:

In this study thorough diagnosis of uterus and endometrium tubes was done by the HSG and hysteroscopy. In this study positive aspects of this study was also concluded for example it is cost effective, assures the patients comfort, and yield in

good understanding of all the minor and major problems in the uterine.

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